

Application of Machine Learning in Wetland Management and Conservation

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Abstract

Wetlands are a mix of aquatic and terrestrial vital ecosystems and hence they offer unique habitat for several species. They help to protect the biodiversity and offer several ecosystem services. But due to anthropogenic and climate change threats they are prone to serious damage and deterioration. Hence wetland management and conservation are of significance. In such a scenario, machine learning models come as a rescue towards their monitoring, management and conservation. This article highlights the machine learning models that can help in the management and conservation of wetlands.

Key words: Wetlands, Management, Conservation, Algorithms.

Introduction

Water is the elixir of life. Without water there is no life. Though we have a large amount of water on earth, most of it is not of direct use as it has too much of salt. Total amount of fresh water available on our earth is only about 84.4 million cubic km. Freshwater is required for many life supporting activities like drinking, agriculture, transport, and power generation. Freshwater ecosystems, like lakes, rivers, streams, and wetlands, inhabit more animal species

despite being less than 1% of the surface of our earth.

Wetlands occur as aquatic systems or marshes, bogs, mangroves, mudflats, and floodplains. Most wetlands are a mix of various types of freshwater ecosystems. Wetlands are found in all continents except Antarctica. Broadly, the two types of wetlands include coastal wetlands and inland wetlands. Wetlands support both aquatic and terrestrial organisms. The continued existence of water highly favours growth of hydrophytes. A wide

variety of birds and mammals live in wetlands. Wetlands also harbour many types of fish species.

Wetlands are aquatic environments and may be covered by freshwater, saltwater, or a mix and they are not often given due importance. They serve as natural systems of waste-water treatment and carbon storage. They play a major role in food security. Millions of people find their livelihoods in wetlands. They offer field for rice cultivation, an economically important food crop. They control flood, provide water, storm protection, and economically and medically important materials. They trap contaminants like phosphorus and heavy metals and convert nitrogen into a usable form for plants to accumulate.

Although wetlands occupy a relatively small area of the Earth's surface, their carbon sequestration capacity is significant. They store more carbon than rainforests, helping to limit greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate global warming and climate change. Wetlands lock natural carbon-rich waste in their sediments. As these ecosystems develop rapidly and maintain stability, they become increasingly effective at removing

carbon from the Wetlands face significant damage from industrial pollution, climate change, dam construction, agriculture, aquaculture, and urban development. More wetlands have been lost in the past three centuries than ever before. The reduction of wetlands forces developed cities to incur higher costs for water treatment and flood control. Therefore, monitoring the quality of water and soil in wetland areas is crucial for conserving and protecting these unique and vital ecosystems. While conventional environmental monitoring methods are widely used by agencies, they are often limited by practical challenges (Singh et al., 2023). Machine learning models offer a promising alternative for wetland management and conservation, providing several advantages over traditional methods.

Machine learning utilizes algorithms to analyze data and predict new information (Msomi and Mabuwa, 2020; Saxena and Lal, 2012). It is widely applied across various disciplines due to its precision, flexibility, and convenience (Joy et al., 2021). Machine learning can handle complex, nonlinear relational data and uncovering underlying mechanisms

(Godavarthi et al., 2017). Its adaptability makes it a powerful tool for wetland management and conservation. By leveraging machine learning, more accurate assessments can be conducted for monitoring water quality (Kumari et al., 2021).

Water from different ecosystems exhibits significant complexity (Saxena et al., 2012), posing substantial challenges for water quality analysis and monitoring. Machine learning models offer effective solutions to address these challenges. They can be applied to various aspects of water analysis,

treatment, and monitoring, providing innovative approaches to tackle complex problems.

The application of machine learning in water research marks a significant advancement (Agrawal et al., 2023; Arun et al., 2015). Numerous water quality prediction models have been developed (Table 1), with efforts focused on optimizing these models to enhance their prediction accuracy. Machine learning algorithms can be effectively utilized for the management and conservation of wetlands (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2).

Table 1. Some machine learning models used in wetland management and conservation

Matrix factorization	Long short-term memory	LASSO, Ridge regression	PROGOL	FOIL
Linear determinant analysis	Principal component analysis	Shrinkage estimates	Generalised Linear Model	Gradient Boosted Trees
Bayesian network	Neocognitron	Fuzzy Inference Systems	Generalised Additive Model	Boosted regression trees
Gaussian mixture model	CNN precursor	First consumer CPU	Feed-forward neural network	Classification Trees
Self-organizing map	Bootstrap	Gradient Boosting	Multi layer neural network	Decision Trees
Region-based convolutional network	Jackknife	k-nearest neighbor	Graph neural network	Regression Trees
Deep belief network	Genetic Algorithm	Convolutional neural network	Recurrent Neural Network	Random Forests
Projection Pursuit Regression	Naïve Bayes	Bayesian Methods	Artificial Neural Network	Boosted Trees
k-Means	Multi-layer Perceptron	Support Vector Machines	Deep neural networks	Bagged Trees

Fig.1. Overview of Machine learning in Wetland Management

Fig.2. Overview of Machine learning in Wetland Conservation

Conclusion

Machine learning can serve as a valuable tool to address challenges in wetland environments, as it can be applied to predict water quality, monitor biodiversity, conserve species, and identify threats from anthropogenic activities and climate change. However, there are several challenges in applying machine learning: (1) Machine learning relies on the collection of large datasets, which is difficult to achieve in wetlands; (2) Due to the complexity of field

conditions, algorithms may only be applicable to limited systems; (3) Using machine learning algorithms requires ecologists to possess foundational knowledge in the field. To overcome these challenges, the following measures can be taken in the future: (1) More advanced sensors should be employed for quality monitoring to gather data; (2) The reliability of models needs to be improved; (3) Interdisciplinary training in various fields should be provided to develop advanced machine learning techniques.

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